

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XIX. Synthesis of 1,3,4-Thiadiazolines and Di-1,3,4-thiadiazolines

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A number of 1, 3, 4-thiadiazolines and di-1,3,4-thiadiazolines have been prepared with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

Recently Surrey *et al.*¹ and others²⁻³ have shown that thiazole derivatives possess high antiamoebic activity *in vitro* as well as the ability to form metallic complexes. A nitrogen atom would be expected to activate an -NH-group more than a carbon atom. The thiadiazolines, possessing an -NH-group adjacent to nitrogen atom (1,3,4-thiadiazolines), are excellent chelating agents⁴⁻⁶. These are derived from thiosemicarbazones which also possess good chelating properties⁷⁻⁹. Since some chelating agents, e.g., 8-hydroxyquinolines, possess marked antiamoebic properties, it is possible that thiadiazolines may also possess such activity.

In the present investigation, a number of 1,3,4-thiadiazolines (I) and di-1,3,4-thiadiazolines (II) have been prepared with a view to studying their antiamoebic activity.

The required 5-(alkyl-and aryl-imino-)-2-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazolines were obtained by cyclising 4-alkyl- and 4-aryl-thiosemicarbazones either with alkaline potassium ferrocyanide¹⁰ or with ethanolic iodine; 5-(alkyl- and aryl-imino-)-2-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolines were obtained by treating the appropriate thiosemicarbazides (4-phenyl, 4-cyclohexyl, 4-*p*-phenetyl, and 4-*o*-SH-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide) with appropriate acid chloride (acetyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride, dichloroacetyl chloride, and dimethylaminoacetyl chloride hydrochloride) in dry thiophene-free benzene.

1. Surrey and Cutler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 578.
2. Kaushiva, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, **15C**, 160; 1957, **16C**, 210.
3. Brown *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1544.
4. Pujari *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 701.
5. B. P. 811, 115/1959; *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, **53**, 17527.
6. *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, **53**, 123.
7. Holzbecher, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 809.
8. Guha Sircar *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 450.
9. Mitra *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, **32**, 435.
10. Ramachander *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21C**, 44.

4-Alkyl- and 4-aryl-thiosemicarbazones were prepared by refluxing appropriate aryl aldehydes with appropriate 4-alkyl- or 4-aryl-thiosemicarbazides in ethanol. The latter were obtained essentially by the method of Kazakov *et al.*¹¹.

Dimethylaminoacetic acid hydrochloride was prepared by a more convenient method.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Alkyl- and 4-Aryl-thiosemicarbazides

The appropriate amine (0.1M) was dissolved in ammonia solution (20ml, d 0.888) and CS₂ (8ml) was added to it gradually with stirring and cooling below 30°. Ethanol (20-25 ml) was then added and stirring continued till CS₂ had completely dissolved. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours and a solution of sodium chloroacetate (0.1M) was added, followed by hydrazine hydrate (10 ml, 50%) or hydrazine sulphate (0.15 M, dissolved in 20 ml ammonia solution). It was warmed and then filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to half its volume and allowed to stand overnight. The crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

When a diamine (0.1M) was used, the amounts of the reactants were doubled. The yields, m.p.'s and analyses of these are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Amine condensed.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	Aniline	90%	*140°	C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ S	..	..	..	..
2.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	88	§144°	C ₈ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S	..	..	..	..
3.	<i>o</i> -Aminobenzene-thiol	98	177°	C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	20.98	21.10	32.20	32.16
4.	Benzidine	60	> 280°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ S ₂	25.40	25.30	19.31	19.27
5.	Cyclohexylamine	50	‡143°	C ₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	..	..	..	..
6.	Ethylenediamine	56	‡221°	C ₄ H ₁₂ N ₆ S ₂	..	..	..	..
7.	2-Amino-4-ethylthiazole	57	180°	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂	27.58	27.72	31.60	31.68

*Fulvermacher (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 615) report the same m.p.

§Busch (*ibid.*, 1902, 35, 1714) report the same m.p.

‡Kazakov *et al.*¹¹ report the same m.p.

4-Alkyl- and 4-Aryl-thiosemicarbazones

Equimolecular quantities of the appropriate 4-alkyl- or 4-aryl-thiosemicarbazide and appropriate aryl aldehyde were refluxed in ethanol on a water bath for 1 hour. It was allowed to stand overnight and crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The yields, m.p.'s and analyses of these are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	R'.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
R = Phenyl.						
1.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Ph	96%	190°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₃ ClS	14.46	14.23
2.	<i>p</i> -OH, <i>m</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	99	170°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	13.90	13.95
3.	Furfuryl	95	182°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S	17.20	17.14
4.	Vinyl-Ph	98	165°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	14.78	14.84
5.	β -Naphthyl	92	210°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	13.78	13.80
R = Cyclohexyl.						
6.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	88	166°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₃ S	13.45	13.42
7.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	90	184°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ON ₃ S	15.20	15.16
8.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Ph	92	220°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ON ₃ ClS	13.40	13.50
9.	Vinyl-Ph	90	215°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ S	14.58	14.53
10.	Furfuryl	95	163°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	15.30	15.27
R = <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl.						
11.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	98	188°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ON ₄ S	17.02	17.07
12.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	92	164°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	14.10	14.04
13.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	95	184°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	14.78	14.75
14.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	96	196°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	13.35	14.41
15.	Vinyl-Ph	93	182°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	13.50	13.41
R = <i>o</i> -SH-phenyl.						
16.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	84	178°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	13.99	13.95
17.	Ph	86	181°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.68	14.63
18.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	90	120°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S ₂	13.85	13.86
19.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	82	182°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₃ S ₂	13.30	13.24
20.	Furfuryl	78	153°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S ₂	15.20	15.16
R = 4-Ethylthiazolyl.						
21.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	69	240°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ S ₂	21.20	21.02
22.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	72	193°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂	19.48	19.43
23.	Ph	65	193°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	19.35	19.31 ^a
24.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	63	188°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S ₂	17.60	17.50
25.	Furfuryl	65	178°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₄ S ₂	20.08	20.00

^aPh = phenyl.

With thiosemicarbazides of the type (NH₂.NH.CS.NH)₂.X, two-molecular proportion of appropriate aryl aldehyde was condensed. The yields, m.p's and analyses of these are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	R.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
$X = CH_2-CH_2-$						
1.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph*	68%	232°	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ S ₂	23.75	23.82
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	70	230°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂	26.78	26.92
3.	<i>m</i> -OH-Ph	70	240°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	20.22	20.19
4.	Vinyl-Ph	65	225°	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₆ S ₂	19.00	19.09
5.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	75	170°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	18.96	18.91

6.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	65	224°	C ₃₂ H ₃₄ N ₆ S ₂ ^c	18.00	18.85
7.	Ph	70	223°	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂	16.60	16.53
8.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	68	> 280°	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	15.60	15.55
9.	Vinyl-Ph	60	235°	C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₆ S ₂	14.85	14.89
10.	Furfuryl	62	220°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	17.25	17.21

*Ph=phenyl.

5-(Alkyl- and Aryl-imino)-2-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazolines

Method (I).—The appropriate thiosemicarbazone was dissolved in EtOH-NaOH solution with a little water (5 ml) and heated on a water bath; a 5% aqueous solution of potassium ferricyanide was added dropwise and with shaking until further precipitation had ceased. The precipitate was filtered, washed several times with hot water to remove adhering potassium ferricyanide, and recrystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide or ethanol.

Method (II).—A mixture of iodine (0.1*M*), dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and the appropriate arylthiosemicarbazone (0.1*M*) was refluxed for 5 to 6 hours and allowed to stand overnight. The separated crystals were filtered, washed with a 1% sodium thio-sulphate solution and water, and recrystallised from ethanol, giving dihydroiodide of the corresponding thiadiazoline.

Free thiadiazoline base was liberated by treating the dihydroiodide with excess of ammonia solution (*d* 0.888) followed by concentrating the solution on a water bath till the smell of ammonia had dissipated. The separated crystals were filtered, washed with little water and recrystallised from ethanol. The yields, m.p.'s, and analyses of these are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	R.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
R=Phenyl.						
1.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Ph†	74%	186°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ ClS	14.65	14.80
2.	<i>p</i> -OH, <i>m</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	75	*256°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ I ₂ S	7.90	7.74
3.	Furfuryl	65	160°	C ₁₂ H ₉ ON ₃ S	17.30	17.28
4.	Vinyl-Ph	70	*230°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ I ₂ S	7.90	7.82
5.	β -Naphthyl	64	157°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	13.90	13.86
R=Cyclohexyl.						
6.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	52	152°	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ S	18.60	18.54
7.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	48	132°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	15.30	15.27
8.	<i>o</i> -Cl-Ph	50	*230°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ON ₃ ClI ₂ S	7.48	7.43
9.	Vinyl-Ph	58	150°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ S	14.65	14.63
10.	Furfuryl	60	135°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ON ₃ S	15.50	15.48
R= <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl.						
11.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	80	190°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₄ S	17.20	17.17
12.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	78	*265°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ I ₂ S	7.85	7.79
13.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	75	*240°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₃ I ₂ S	7.58	7.53
14.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	68	172°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	13.48	13.41
15.	Vinyl-Ph	70	146°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	13.60	13.54
R= <i>o</i> -SH-phenyl.						
16.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	85	148°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.10	14.04
17.	Ph	84	153°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂	14.60	14.73
18.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	88	130°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂	13.90	13.85
19.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	78	149°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ON ₄ S ₂	13.45	13.39
20.	Furfuryl	80	136°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₄ S ₂	15.30	15.27
R=4-Ethylthiazolyl.						
21.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	64	168°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	21.42	21.11
22.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	68	*250°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ I ₂ S ₂	10.10	10.03
23.	Ph	65	*272°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ I ₂ S ₂	10.30	10.23
24.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	70	*380°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ON ₄ I ₂ S ₂	9.61	9.75
25.	Furfuryl	72	*268°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ON ₄ I ₂ S ₂	10.52	10.46

† Ph=phenyl.

*As dihydroiodide.

The arylthiosemicarbazones of the type (R-C=N-NH.CS.NH)₂-X were cyclised by method (II) using 0.2 *M* of iodine for 0.1 *M* of thiosemicarbazone. These were recrystallised from aqueous dimethylformamide. Their yields, m.p.'s and analyses are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

No.	R.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
X = CH ₂ -CH ₂ -						
1.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph*	58%	210°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ S ₂	24.15	24.03
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluo	54	215°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂	27.25	27.30
3.	<i>m</i> -OH-Ph	60	207°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	20.25	20.38
4.	Vinyl-Ph	55	212°	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂	19.84	19.92
5.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ -Ph	60	205°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	19.15	19.09

6.	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ -Ph	56	198°	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₆ S ₂	18.77	18.98
7.	Ph	58	200°	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂	16.60	16.66
8.	<i>o</i> -OH-Ph	60	204°	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	15.65	15.67
9.	Vinyl-Ph	58	220°	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₆ S ₂	15.04	15.00
10.	Furfuryl	55	209°	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ S ₂	17.30	17.36

*Ph = phenyl.

Dimethylaminoacetic acid hydrochloride was conveniently prepared as follows: Chloroacetic acid (47.5 g., 5 *M*) was added portionwise to 25% aqueous dimethylamine solution (200 ml) with stirring at 0°. The mixture was set aside in the cold for 24 hours and afterwards at room temperature for further 24 hours. It was then evaporated on a water bath after the addition of 5*N*-NaOH solution (200 ml) till excess dimethylamine had disappeared. The solution was acidified (Congo red), filtered from precipitated sodium chloride, and evaporated again to a syrup. The syrup was taken in absolute ethanol and filtered. Ethanol was distilled, the residue was triturated with methanol, and acetone was added dropwise till no further precipitate was obtained. This was filtered and recrystallised from methanol-acetone mixture as colorless crystals, m.p. 180° (lit.²², m.p. 176-78°), yield 22 g. (30%). (Found: N, 10.00; neut. equiv., 71.0. Calc. for C₄H₁₁O₂NCl: N, 9.96%; neut. equiv., 70.25).

The acid chloride hydrochloride of the above acid was prepared by refluxing the dried and well-ground acid (0.1*M*) and thionyl chloride (0.15*M*) in dry thiophene-free benzene (50 ml) for ½ hr. Benzene and excess thionyl chloride were then distilled in *vacuo* and the residual brown acid chloride was used in the next step.

5-(*Alkyl- and Aryl-imino*)-2-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazosines.—Appropriate 4-alkyl- or 4-aryl-thiosemicarbazide (0.1*M*) and appropriate acid chloride (0.1*M*) were refluxed together in dry thiophene-free benzene (20 ml) for 30 mins. and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The separated crystals were filtered, washed with 1% sodium

bicarbonate solution, then with water, and finally recrystallised from ethanol. Their yields, m.p.'s and analyses are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI

No.	R.	R'.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	CH ₃	65%	162°	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ S	15.94	15.90
2	"	CHCl ₂	54	165°	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	11.45	11.42
3	"	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	44	184°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ S	20.00	19.99
4	Cyclohexyl	CH ₂ Cl	50	198°	C ₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClS	12.85	12.81
5	"	CHCl ₂	46	210°	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	11.20	11.11
6	"	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	42	193°	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ S	18.50	18.58
7	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -phenyl	CH ₂ Cl	56	158°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClS	11.52	11.81
8	"	CHCl ₂	50	155°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.20	10.14
9	"	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	50	170°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ON ₃ S	16.75	16.80
10	<i>o</i> -SH-phenyl	CH ₃	55	100°	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂	13.42	13.48
11	"	CHCl ₂	48	185°	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	10.18	10.10
12	"	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	48	188°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂	16.64	16.60

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